

Radiation Stability of Inorganic Exchangers-II

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Synthetic inorganic exchangers have been studied extensively because of their reported high selectivity for certain ions, stability towards temperature and radiation¹ and their wide application². The effects of radiation on the characteristics of some inorganic exchangers have been studied by a few authors³. In this laboratory, methods were developed for the separation of K Ci amounts of fission products using synthetic inorganic exchangers. Investigations are being made to evaluate the stability of these exchangers in presence of gamma radiation. The results of studies on ammonium phosphomolybdate and hydrous manganese dioxide subjected to 10⁶ and 10⁷ Gy of gamma dose have been reported⁴. The present communication describes the results of detailed studies carried out on polyantimonic acid (PA) and zirconium antimonate (ZrA) which are to be used on a pilot scale operation in the flow sheet for the separation of ⁹⁰Sr and ¹⁴⁴Ce from spent fuel waste solution.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the distribution coefficients obtained for the elements strontium on PA and sodium on ZrA irradiated to 10 MGy in presence of 2 M nitric acid. As seen from the results, there is only marginal variation in the values obtained before and after irradiation. The observed variations appear to be well within experimental limits. The results with other conditions of irradiation are also similar. The percentages of antimony in PA and antimony and zirconium in ZrA before and after irradiation are given in Table 2. These results also show that there is no significant change in chemical composition due to irradiation and the slight differences observed may be due to experimental variations. Table 3 gives the total exchange capacities of these exchangers for the respective elements from

TABLE 1-DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS : 10⁷ GY WET (ml/g)

HNO ₃ M	PA-Sr		ZrA-Na	
	Control	Irradiated	Control	Irradiated
0.2	8.0 × 10 ³	7.2 × 10 ³	1.5 × 10 ⁴	1.4 × 10 ⁴
0.5	2.1 × 10 ³	2.1 × 10 ³	5.5 × 10 ³	5.4 × 10 ³
1.0	1.6 × 10 ³	1.8 × 10 ³	4.4 × 10 ³	6.3 × 10 ³
2.0	1.6 × 10 ³	1.7 × 10 ³	2.8 × 10 ³	5.6 × 10 ³
4.0	6.8 × 10 ²	4.8 × 10 ²	1.2 × 10 ³	1.6 × 10 ³
6.0	1.1 × 10 ²	7.4 × 10	6.4 × 10 ²	1.3 × 10 ³
8.0	3.0 × 10	2.2 × 10	3.7 × 10 ²	7.0 × 10 ²
10.0	1.9 × 10	1.3 × 10	2.8 × 10 ²	4.2 × 10 ²

simulated fission product waste solution (Type-I) and there is not much variation in the values.

Fig. 1 shows some typical breakthrough curves obtained from simulated fission product solution Type-I for elements Sr on PA and Na on ZrA before and after irradiation. It is observed that the curves show a general sigmoid pattern almost similar to each other.

Polyantimonic acid (PA) : The X-ray diffractograms of PA both control and irradiated to 1 MGy in presence of 2 M nitric acid are almost similar indicating that PA does not undergo any observable change in

TABLE 2-CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

Exchanger	Element	Control %	Irradiated (%)	
			10 MGy dry	10 MGy with 2 M HNO ₃
ZrA	Zr	2.3	2.4	2.4
ZrA	Sb	55.2	55.2	55.8
PA	Sb	59.3	58.9	60.4

Fig 1 Breakthrough curves of sodium on ZrA (A) irradiated to 10^7 Gy with 2 M HNO_3 , (B) control, and curves of strontium on (C) irradiated to 10^7 Gy with 2 M HNO_3 , (D) control

TABLE 3—TOTAL EXCHANGE CAPACITY

Exchanger	Element	Total Exchange capacity (mg/g)		
		Control	Irradiated to 10 MGy dry	Irradiated to 10 MGy with 2 M HNO_3
PA	Si	1.45	1.45	1.6
ZrA	Na	12.6	-	12.6

the crystal structure after irradiation. The ir spectra of PA both control and irradiated samples, are almost identical showing thereby that PA does not undergo any drastic change in molecular structure due to irradiation. The thermograms of PA obtained before and after irradiation are identical and are superimposed on each other showing that both the control and irradiated samples possess the same weight loss characteristics.

Zirconium antimonate (ZrA) : The X-ray diffractograms of unirradiated and irradiated ZrA appear to be almost same and the relative intensities are of the same order indicating that there is no significant change in the crystal structure due to irradiation. The ir spectra of ZrA before and after gamma irradiation reveal no apparent differences between control and irradiated samples showing that the chemical structure remains unaltered after the irradiation. In case of the thermograms of ZrA control and irradiated samples, the weight-loss is less than 20% up to 950° and the shape

of the curves is similar indicating no significant change due to irradiation.

Conclusion : The results of the various investigations indicate that the properties of the materials do not undergo detectable changes as a result of irradiation up to 10^7 Gy by gamma rays.

Experimental

The exchangers were supplied by M/s. Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar. All the reagents used were of G.R. (E. Merck) or AnalaR grade and the tracers were available with Isotope Division. Irradiation was carried out using either a Gama Chamber-900 or Panoramic Batch Irradiator of Isotope Division. 20 g portions of the exchanger either in the dry form or slurred with 2 M HNO_3 were irradiated in screw capped vials or s.s. capsules to a total dose of 1 and 10 MGy. Distribution coefficients were evaluated by standard radiometric techniques. Antimony in PA and ZrA and zirconium in ZrA were estimated using regular analytical methods.

Breakthrough patterns and exchange capacities were determined radiometrically with 2 g of exchanger in glass columns using simulated fission product waste solution spiked with appropriate radioactive tracers. X-Ray diffraction studies were carried out using a Siemens diffractometer with copper K_α radiation of wavelength 1.54184 Å. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. TGA was done using a Mettler TA-1 thermoanalyser.

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